

REVIEWING THE LEGAL STATUS OF EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS IN THE MINISTRY OF INTERNAL AFFAIRS SYSTEM IN MODERN CIVIL LAW IS A REQUIREMENT OF THE TIME

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Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Law

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17529252>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 29th October 2025

Accepted: 30th October 2025

Online: 31st October 2025

KEYWORDS

educational institutions of the Ministry of Internal Affairs system, paid educational services, academic (financial) freedom.

ABSTRACT

This article substantiates the need to revise the legal status of educational institutions within the Ministry of Internal Affairs system due to the increasing integration of market economy principles into social life and the growth of competitive educational services in our country.

Uzbekistan's transition to a market economy, as in all spheres, has created competition in the field of education. The fact that the market economy is based on free commodity-money relations and the movement of various forms of services has accelerated these processes. It is known that during the Soviet era, all types of education were provided free of charge, and this was enshrined at the constitutional level (Article 43 of the Constitution of the Uzbek SSR) [1]. However, the market economy system created the need for educational institutions to be self-sufficient and to provide paid educational services. As a result of such situations, there is a need to revise the civil legal status of educational institutions that did not need to operate as legal entities during the Soviet period.

The transition of the Republic of Uzbekistan to a market economy has made paid education and paid educational services the subject of civil law contracts, and these provisions are reflected in our national legislation. In particular, Article 6 of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Education" of August 29, 1997, stipulated that "Educational institutions have the right to provide paid educational services in accordance with their statutory tasks, as well as to engage in other types of entrepreneurial activity" [2].

The increasing integration of market economy principles into public life in our country has made the participation of educational institutions, including those within the system of the Ministry of Internal Affairs (hereinafter - MIA), in civil turnover an objective necessity. Indeed, today educational institutions are widely involved in civil law relations, especially in property relations related to the provision of paid educational services.

The specific complexity of determining the legal status of educational institutions in the MIA system is determined by:

Firstly, educational institutions of various forms (schools, lyceums, academies, centers, etc.) operate in the MIA system, and the legal status of each of them has special characteristics;

Secondly, the activities of educational institutions within the MIA system are regulated by various levels of legislation. In particular, the Civil Code (hereinafter - CC), general laws (for example, on non-governmental non-profit organizations) and special laws (for example, on education) are in effect.

It should be especially noted that the reforms aimed at improving the legal status of educational institutions as legal entities and expanding their participation in civil law relations in our country were carried out mainly in two stages. In the first stage, educational institutions were granted the right to provide paid educational services and engage in entrepreneurial activity, and in the second stage, the establishment and operation of private educational institutions were permitted.

According to M.V. Grechko, the basis for the emergence of private educational institutions was the recognition of private property in society and the recognition of the equality of all forms of ownership. However, in our opinion, the recognition of private property and ensuring the equality of all forms of ownership is one of the important principles of a market economy. Therefore, the basis for the emergence of private educational institutions was not the recognition of the equality of private property and forms of ownership in society, but the country's transition to a market economy. In other words, without the transition to a market economy, there would be no equality of private property and forms of ownership in society.

Indeed, according to the traditional rule formed in civil law, legal entities are divided into commercial and non-commercial types based on their property rights and the nature of their activities. As A. S. Fedoryashenko noted, "due to the lack of permission for entrepreneurial activity in Soviet civil law, there was no division of legal entities into commercial and non-commercial types"[4]. That is, the Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan divides legal entities into commercial and non-commercial types. And this is reflected in the first part of Article 40 of the Civil Code in the following content: "An organization that has made profit as the main goal of its activity (commercial organization) or does not make profit as such a goal (non-commercial organization) can be a legal entity."[5] When dividing legal entities into such types, their main goals and the procedure for using the income received are taken into account as criteria. That is, if the main goal of commercial organizations is to make a profit and distribute this profit among the participants who created it, then the real goal of non-commercial organizations (including educational institutions) is aimed at fulfilling socio-cultural tasks. It should be noted that our national legislation also allows non-commercial organizations (including educational institutions) to engage in entrepreneurial and income-generating activities. However, it is not allowed that such activity becomes their main activity and the profit obtained as a result of it is distributed among the participants.

Naturally, the market economy has transformed non-commercial legal entities into active subjects of civil law relations. Paragraph 3 of Chapter 4 of the Civil Code, Articles 7-78, lists 6 forms of non-commercial organizations. However, the law does not prohibit the creation of other forms of non-commercial organizations. That is, Article 40 of the Civil Code provides that non-commercial organizations may be created in another form provided for by law.

The most common legal form of non-commercial organizations are institutions, which play a special role in ensuring and implementing the interests of the state and society. For example, "educational institutions" with civil law status play an important role in training strong and competitive mature personnel necessary for the affairs of the state and society. As is known, in our country, the creation of private educational institutions is permitted precisely for the purpose of training competent and competitive personnel. These processes have created a unique new trend in the market of educational services, and as a result, new organizational and legal forms of educational organizations (private, international, etc.) have appeared.

According to A.A. Popov, "The active involvement of institutions in civil circulation, that is, the performance of non-commercial functions on the one hand and active participation in property relations on the other, creates the need to revise their legal status in civil legal relations"[6]. Indeed, the emergence of private educational institutions and the competitive environment in the process of personnel training have created the need to revise the organizational and legal status of state educational institutions, such as the implementation of traditional management and other non-commercial functions, full or partial financial support by the founders. The implementation of this will allow solving the problems associated with the participation of relatively new institutions among the subjects of civil law in civil law relations. In addition, as private educational institutions develop in the education market today with their paid and competitive educational services, it also serves to make educational institutions in the system of the Ministry of Internal Affairs a subject of decent competition.

Educational institutions in the system of the Ministry of Internal Affairs, on the one hand, are a structure in the system of the ministry, which is a state governing body, and on the other hand, are a subject in the group of non-profit organizations, that is, an institution with the status of a legal entity. In this context, it is necessary to pay attention to a number of features of the activities of educational institutions of the Ministry of Internal Affairs system:

Firstly, the activities of educational institutions in the system of the Ministry of Internal Affairs consist of activities both in the system of a state governing body[7] and as a non-commercial legal entity, i.e., an institution;

Secondly, the activities of educational institutions in the system of the Ministry of Internal Affairs, along with the implementation of socio-cultural or other non-commercial tasks, carry out special activities related to the performance of tasks assigned to internal affairs bodies on the basis of Article 2 of the Law "On Internal Affairs Bodies."

Speaking about the activities of educational institutions of the Ministry of Internal Affairs system, it is necessary to emphasize that it is, first of all, an organization created by the owner and fully or partially financed for the training of qualified specialists for internal affairs bodies, that is, for the implementation of socio-cultural or other non-commercial tasks defined in Article 76 of the Civil Code.

In this regard, in the context of a market economy and educational competition, the issue of competition between educational institutions of the Ministry of Internal Affairs system and educational institutions granted academic freedom (financial independence) in the training of qualified personnel is also relevant. Indeed, the number of educational

institutions granted academic freedom (financial independence) in our country is increasing year by year.

As established in Article 76 of the Civil Code, educational institutions with the status of institutions are organizations created by the owner for the implementation of managerial, socio-cultural, or other non-commercial functions, but it cannot be denied that they also actively participate in relations related to entrepreneurial activity. In other words, even if educational services are provided by non-profit organizations, their paid educational services are the subject of the contract for the provision of paid services. This means that educational institutions of the Ministry of Internal Affairs system are also included in the subjective composition of fee-paying service providers.

The Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated December 24, 2021 No. PP-61 "On Measures to Grant Financial Independence to State Higher Educational Institutions"[8] significantly increased the participation of educational institutions in civil law relations, including educational institutions of the Ministry of Internal Affairs system. In other words, this legal document became the legal basis for reforms related to changing the organizational and legal forms of educational institutions, that is, the formation of modern educational institutions that meet the requirements of a market economy. According to this decree, starting January 1, 2022, 35 higher education institutions in Uzbekistan began operating on the basis of academic independence. It should be especially noted that the new provision, included in part 2 of Article 51 of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the new edition, adopted by popular vote in the referendum of the Republic of Uzbekistan held on April 30, 2023, "Higher educational institutions have the right to academic freedom, self-government, freedom of research and teaching in accordance with the law"[9], caused a revolutionary change in the activities of educational institutions.

As a result of academic independence, higher educational institutions (hereinafter - HEIs) independently solve a number of important tasks, such as determining curricula, programs, qualification requirements, forms of education, study duration, additional admission to doctoral studies with the allocation of grants at their own expense, introducing correspondence, distance and evening education for master's programs, creating and publishing textbooks and other educational and scientific literature under their own seal, internal control of the quality of education, attracting local and foreign professors, teachers and specialists on a contractual basis, and directly purchasing foreign educational and scientific literature, textbooks, and teaching aids.

The rapid entry of not only private, but also foreign and international educational institutions into the educational market of Uzbekistan with paid educational services created competition in the educational market and ultimately contributed to the modernization of state educational institutions. These processes were also implemented in the activities of educational institutions of the Ministry of Internal Affairs system. In particular, by the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated August 16, 2017 No. PP-3216 "On Measures for the Fundamental Improvement of the System of Training, Retraining and Advanced Training of Employees of Internal Affairs Bodies," starting from the 2018/2019 academic year, a correspondence form of education was introduced, and training was organized on a paid-contract basis. Also, by the Decree of the President of the Republic of

Uzbekistan dated August 18, 2023 No. PP-282, amendments and additions were made to the above-mentioned Decree No. PP-3216, providing for the annual admission quota of 700 people to the Academy for full-time education, as well as an additional 200 people on a paid-contract basis[10].

In our opinion, ensuring, in accordance with the law, the right of state educational institutions, including educational institutions of the Ministry of Internal Affairs, to academic freedom, self-government, freedom of research and teaching, freedom to independently carry out the main directions of their activities, and the right to independence in making decisions on determining the procedure and conditions of education is becoming a requirement of the times. The intense competitive environment in our country's education market necessitates a sharp reduction in the independent operation of educational institutions, inappropriate interference by higher organizations and their officials in the activities of educational institutions, and instructing educational institutions on the conditions and requirements for conducting training. In a word, today's processes indicate the need for a radical change in the form of management inherited from the former Soviet system in relation to educational institutions.

In conclusion, it can be said that in civil law, the definition of the legal characteristics of educational institutions, which are a non-profit organization in the system of the Ministry of Internal Affairs, as a legal entity, is important in their entry into civil legal relations, recognition as a subject of civil law, conclusion of contracts with individuals and legal entities for the provision of paid educational services, resolution of civil disputes with other subjects in court, participation in court as a plaintiff and defendant, legal management of their property. The presence of various educational institutions in the system of the Ministry of Internal Affairs and the specifics of their civil law status require a separate study of each of their legal characteristics as a legal entity.

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